

COMBINATION OF FLOATING LIDAR MEASUREMENTS WITH NUMERICAL MODELLING FOR AN INTEGRATED OFFSHORE WIND RESOURCE ASSESSMENT

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Project abstract:

The increasing interest in developing offshore wind farms has brought to light remote sensing devices as a more flexible and cost-efficient alternative to conventional meteorological masts for measuring relevant wind resources and site conditions. Nowadays, there are several options for employing these devices, such as their installation on wind turbines' platforms, in a buoy, or on a ship. This last option, so-called ship-based lidar technology, consists of a vertical Doppler lidar profiler deployed onboard a vessel. It allows measuring offshore winds and conditions along the vast region covered by the ship track and reduces the cost and complexity of offshore measurements campaigns. The applicability of ship-mounted lidar technology for wind measurements has been already studied during several experiments within the NEWA (New European Wind Atlas) framework. However, this system still needs to overcome particular scientific challenges before a reliable and reproducible methodology for its deployment can be defined, such as the effects of ship movements and the consequent challenge of preserving high-reliable measurements of wind speed and direction, or the complexity to combine these space-variable measurements with other data sources to correlate them with long-term statistics. Under this premise, the overall scope of the Ph.D. project is to investigate how ship-based LiDAR technology should be applied in an optimal way to assess the offshore wind resource and site conditions, both in combination with mesoscale flow modeling and the use of satellite remote sensing data. In the course of this project, four main aspects will be studied in detail:

- The evaluation of the most suitable configuration and setup for ship-based LiDAR technology, as well as its performance and applicability for wind conditions measurement.
- The investigation of the effects of vessel motions on LiDAR measurements quality and the development of a reliable correction methodology to compensate them.
- The definition of an integrated data concept for the combination of ship-based LiDAR measurements with numerical modeling and satellite remote sensing data for assessing offshore wind resources and site conditions.
- The design and implementation of a comprehensive uncertainty model for ship-based systems measurements.

Additionally, a central part of the project will be the design, preparation, execution, and data evaluation of a new measurement campaign. This campaign will be built on the experiences from the NEWA Ferry Lidar experiment and will be an opportunity for integrating the novel findings (e.g. optimal LiDAR technology to be used, different methodologies for data processing, assessment of ship influence on measurements, etc.) acquired during previous analyses. Acknowledges: This Ph.D. is part of the Lidar Knowledge Europe (LIKE) project funded by the EU Horizon 2020. The LIKE project aims to foster the training and education of young researchers on emerging laser-based wind measurement technologies and their translation into industrial applications.

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DATA COLLECTION

What data will you collect or create?

The data used in this PhD project can be divided into two different groups:

1. **Ship-based lidar measurements:** this category is composed of ship-based lidar systems observation (and additional equipment) obtained during the execution of the following measurement campaigns:

- The NEWA Ferry Lidar Experiment: this is one of the several experiments conducted as part of the New European Wind Atlas ([NEWA](#)) project. This experiment started in February 2017 and ended in June 2017. During this period, a Windcube v2 (WLS7) vertical profiler lidar was installed on board of the ferry boat Victoria Seaways, that operates on the Route from Kiel, Germany, to Klaipeda, Lithuania, in the Southern Baltic Sea.

The data set consists of raw and 10-min. averaged data recorded by the aforementioned lidar device, measuring wind speed and directions at 12 height levels up to 275 m ASL (Above Sea Level). The lidar device has a sampling resolution of around 0.7 s per line-of-sight (LoS) measurement and it measures successively at four azimuthal positions along a cone with a half-opening angle of 28° followed by a vertical beam. The complete data set includes also the measurements from a weather station (including temperature, pressure, relative humidity and pressure) as well as the height-resolution motion information recorded by a satellite compass and an inertial measurement unit (IMU).

- RV Merian and RV Meteor measurement campaign: as part of the European project [EUREC4A](#), a new ship-based measurement campaign was conducted from November 2019 to March 2020. The measurement campaign was divided into two stages:
 - During the first stage, a short-range Windcube v2 (WLS7) vertical profiler was installed on board the research vessel (RV) Merian. This vessel travelled from Emden (Germany) to Barbados island between November 2019 and January 2020, measuring wind speed and conditions at 12 height levels up to 250 m height.
 - In the second stage, the previously mentioned short-range device was installed together with a long-range Windcube WLS70 lidar on board of RV Meteor going from Barbados islands to the Azores. This phase lasted from January to March 2020 and includes wind data measured up to 2000 m height. This device measures wind speed and direction using a VAD (Velocity-Azimuth Display) scanning mode with a sampling rate of approximately 6 s at four azimuthal positions along a cone angle of 14.7°. In this case, there is no vertical beam, thus every 360° scan takes around 24 s.

As during the NEWA campaign, measurements of a weather station, satellite compass and the IMU are available.

- A new measurement campaign: as part of this project, a new ship-based lidar measurement campaign will be designed and executed, based on the knowledge and expertise of previous experiences. Similarly to the preceding campaigns, a wind lidar will be deployed on board of a ship, measuring wind parameters like wind speed, directions and LoS radial velocity, as well as the necessary equipment to measure ship motions. The details of this campaign (e.g. lidar device, measurement period, location...) will be defined on a further stage of the PhD project.

In addition to the experimental data, other important information and documents will accompany the dataset, like installation reports and logbooks or photos taken during the installation.

1. **Numerical weather model datasets:** this group is composed of different numerical model data sets like [ERA5](#) or [NEWA](#). The first one is the latest version of the global reanalysis dataset from the European Center for Medium-Range Forecasts ([ECMWF](#)). The second one is a mesoscale European wind atlas created using a modified [WRF](#) (Weather Research and Forecasting) model. These datasets are open-access and can be freely accessed and downloaded.

How will the data be collected or created?

The creation of new ship-lidar data will be done through the deployment of a new measurement campaign. Since there are no commonly used standards or methodologies for the design and installation of this kind of systems, the experience and knowledge of previously executed campaigns will be used as a guideline for both the execution of this new campaign and to implement a data quality process.

In addition, during the execution of the experiment, real-time monitoring will be implemented. Once the campaign is finished, a consolidated data set will be created as in previous experiments.

With regards to the collected data, measurements from the old measurement campaigns will be collected from the Fraunhofer servers. Furthermore, reanalysis and other open access data sets will be downloaded using the platforms where each data set is stored.

DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Most of the data will be stored following the NetCFD standard. This format allows the inclusion of embedded metadata for its self-description. If NetCFD format is not used, a separated document will provide all the required information for the use and interpretation of the data sets.

For the publication of data description, the [wind energy taxonomies and restringed vocabularies](#) will be applied, and additionally, the [CF convention](#) standard will be used when describing atmospheric parameters.

ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

How will you manage any ethical issues?

Different data sets will be used always in accordance with the data management policies required by the corresponding data owner. If any data need to be transferred, it will be done with the previous consent and following the requirements of the corresponding data owner, as well as in agreement with the procedures established by the Fraunhofer.

If sensitive data (e.g. confidential or personal data) is used during the execution of the project, particular attention will be involved when collecting, processing, handling, and storing this sort of information. For this, a suitable approach will be defined in order to guarantee the data protection, such as the anonymization, pseudonymization or encryption of the stored data, according to the particular ethical and legal requirements.

If no particular requirement is defined, the cloud services provided by Fraunhofer IWES will be used. These platforms allow encrypting information while being transferred and stored, and thus, protecting it from undesired access without the required permission.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

Since this PhD project is part of the LIKE EU consortium, most of the information created during the project will be publicly accessible (e.g. paper publication in peer-reviewed open access journals).

STORAGE AND BACKUP

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

The data and information used over the execution of the project will be stored on the cloud services offered by the Fraunhofer IWES. In addition, and in order to prevent any information and/or data loss, periodical backup copies will be done and stored in the Fraunhofer servers.

During data collection periods, data recorded by different measurement equipment will be stored locally in each system, and internet connection will be used for the transmission of local data to the Fraunhofer servers.

The volume of data to be stored is not certainly known, since it is subject to different undefined factors like the design of the new measurement campaign (equipment used, length of the campaign...) or the amount of different numerical models. However, considering the volume of data of measurement campaigns already executed, an approximation can be made:

- Raw data of the measurement campaign: 30 GW (this includes the observations of lidar devices and the weather station, as well as the ship motions recording)
- Numerical model data sets: 100 GW
- Processed data and results: 80 GW
- Codes and documentation: 2 GW

Indeed, the required data storage capacity will be 212 GW per measurement campaign, meaning a total of around 640 GW for the complete project. This amount of information can be stored in Fraunhofer servers and online platforms like [GitHub](#) (as well as back up copies) without any inconvenient.

How will you manage access and security?

The publicly available data will be uploaded to open source platforms, where users will be able to consult and download it. What regards to no-public data, Fraunhofer provided cloud services will be used to grant access to collaborators. These platforms allow the management of access and users, helping to protect sensitive data and/or information from undesired users.

SELECTION AND PRESERVATION

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

The availability of offshore wind measurements, and particularly, ship-based lidar measurements are still very scarce. For this reason, new ship-lidar observations retrieved during the course of this project may be of great interest in the development of future scientific activities.

Apart from measurements data sets, other relevant information such as processed data, final results, codes and documentation will be examined and evaluated to decide about the need for long-term stored. As indicated before, the complete data set used during the execution of this project will require a storage capacity of less than 1 TB, making it easy to store for long-term preservation for further research.

The long-term storage of public data will meet the FAIR and R5 principles. For that, open-access platforms will be used, and every published deliverable will be complemented with the required information (metadata, data and/or code papers...).

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

All the relevant outcomes of the project will be archived under an appropriate license in a trustworthy repository (Fraunhofer servers).

It must be mentioned, that all shared information will be stored using open-access platforms like [GitHub](#) and [Zenodo](#). The complete long-term stored data will be less than 1 TB, and thus, no extra costs are expected.

DATA SHARING

How will you share the data?

Most of the produced literature, like papers, presentations, data sets, posters or reports will be shared using the platform [Zenodo](#). Codes and code documentation will be shared using [GitHub](#).

With the goal of providing an unmistakable code to all scientific outputs of the author, every deliverable shared will be assigned with a digital identifier [DOI](#). This will be linked to the [ORCID ID](#) of the candidate and/or other involved collaborators.

Additionally, in accordance with the open science principles of this European project, papers publications will be done in peer-review open access journals.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

The newly generated data will be publicly available through open-access platforms. However, the potential restrictions to shareable data will be specifically discussed for each particular project and deliverable with the data owner, to comply with any ethical and legal requirement.

In case any restriction is found when sharing or storing data, a suitable strategy will be investigated (i.e. anonymization, pseudonymization, or encryption) in order to meet the FAIR Data Principles and guarantee data protection.

RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

Who will be responsible for data management?

The responsible for the data management is the PhD student under the revision of his supervisor and in agreement with Fraunhofer data protection policy.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

The execution of the data management plan here described will be done using the available tools provided by Fraunhofer. Additionally, and with the goal of complying with the [FAIR](#) principles for data management, other external and open-access software (like [Zenodo](#), [GitHub](#) or [Python](#)) will be used.